

canonical H3

Sequence alignment for canonical H3 across various species including H. sapiens, S. cerevisiae, D. discoideum, A. thaliana, B. natans, A. limacinum, N. gruberi, T. brucei, M. exilis, T. vaginalis, C. membranifera, C. frisia, Treponomas sp., S. salmonicida, G. muris, and G. intestinalis. The alignment shows conserved regions and divergent sites.

centromeric H3 (CenpA)

Sequence alignment for centromeric H3 (CenpA) across various species including H. sapiens, S. cerevisiae, D. discoideum, A. thaliana, B. natans, A. limacinum, N. gruberi, T. vaginalis, C. membranifera, K. bialata, S. salmonicida, G. muris, and G. intestinalis. The alignment shows conserved regions and divergent sites.



other divergent H3-variants

Sequence alignment for other divergent H3-variants across various species including N. gruberi, C. membranifera, C. frisia, K. bialata, S. salmonicida, G. muris, and G. intestinalis. The alignment shows conserved regions and divergent sites.

